

The FLAIR-GG Virtual Platform - A Network of Germplasm Data Resources Federated via the FAIR Principles

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Plant genetic resources are a significant area of concern for conservation biology and biodiversity. In addition to *in situ* conservation - protection of the environment within which the plant lives - another key source of biodiversity preservation is in the *ex situ* storage of seed in what are known as germplasm banks (GBs). Unfortunately, germplasm bank databases are highly disparate and capture information about their collections in a wide range of underlying data formats, storage platforms, following different standards, and with varying degrees of data accessibility. Thus it is extremely difficult to build conservation strategies for a species integrating data from the GBs conserving the species with data on the species natural distribution. Here, we envisage that the application of the FAIR Principles to germplasm data resources through the creation of a federated network of FAIR germplasm databases, would greatly facilitate cross-resource discovery and exploration for designing more efficient conservation strategies and use of genetic resources.

The FAIR Principles¹ are a set of guidelines for enhancing the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR, or “FAIRness”) of data resources on the Web. FAIR can be implemented in a variety of ways, using a variety of technologies; however, it is most commonly implemented using Semantic Web technologies such as Resource Description Framework² (RDF) and the Web Ontology Language (OWL)³-based ontologies, and generally will separate the resource into two primary concerns: The metadata, and the data they describe. In some, but not all cases, the data itself may be transformed to follow the FAIR principles, particularly in cases where there is significant benefit beyond discoverability, including data integration and/or federated query.

The key features of germplasm data that create a challenge to interoperability are:

1. It is highly dispersed. Worldwide there are an estimated 1,800 seed banks, with more than 7.4 million accessions (in 2010⁴). In Spain, alone, there are approximately 30 seed banks dedicated to crops and crop wild relatives and another 20 seed banks dedicated to wild species.
2. It is (geographically) sparse and biased. Collection expeditions travel to locations where they anticipate certain species will be post-bloom and setting seed. Expeditions are complex to organize, and require multiple levels of permissions, thus many locations remain unsampled or under-sampled.
3. The data is fragmented and of varying precision, due to most observations being generated by-hand in notebooks at time of collection, and most observations preceding the appearance of consumer GPS.
4. There are a surprisingly large number of non-identical plant taxonomies, and additionally, observations may be captured using the plant's common name (and even in the regional language/dialect)
5. The use of controlled vocabularies is limited, and many of the available controlled vocabularies are taxon-specific (for example, the ontologies hosted by Crop Ontology⁵) and focused on crop species, versus wild species.
6. Many germplasm banks - those focused on wild species in particular - are under-resourced compared to other kinds of biological/biomedical databases, and thus have only modest Web interfaces (if any)
7. Germplasm access, and arguably data access also, is controlled at multiple governmental levels, from regional to international, through laws and treaties. The formalization of these constraints into machine-readable/processable formats lags far behind what is the case for other areas of data sharing (e.g. patient consent) and thus access requests must be handled manually.
8. Some Germplasm data - particularly geolocation data for at-risk or endangered species - is extremely sensitive, and is tightly controlled.

Perhaps surprisingly, many of these features are shared in another important domain - the domain of Human Rare Diseases. Rare disease registries are highly dispersed, and predictably, very sparse in their

holdings. They are often single-disease specific, or represent a narrow range of similar diseases. The rarity of the disease often results in a lack of representative phenotypic or disease terminologies or ontology terms. And finally, the data is extremely sensitive, since the rarity of the disease makes personal identification even more likely. With respect to resourcing, however, the European Union has made Rare Disease a core focus of its funding, launching in 2017 the creation of a set of 24 European Reference Networks, focusing on categories of rare diseases, including more than 900 highly focused facilities. Starting in 2019, the European Commission established the European Joint Programme on Rare Disease (EJP-RD). With a total budget exceeding €100 Million, one of the objectives of the EJP-RD project was to build a federated network from these highly dispersed, highly sensitive datasets, using the FAIR Principles as guidelines to improve machine-discoverability and processability, thus minimizing the need for human access to the data. This culminated, in 2024, with the publication of the EJP-RD Virtual Platform and Portal (<https://vp.ejprarediseases.org/>), where a subset of participating rare disease registries can be discovered and accessed in a federated manner.

The FLAIR-GG Network and Portal

In late 2022, the Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación of Spain funded the FAIRification, Linking And Integrated Reuse of Global ex-situ plant Germplasm resources (FLAIR-GG) project, with the goal of building a federated network of Germplasm resources throughout Spain, and globally. The decision was made by the FLAIR-GG project leaders to follow the model of EJP-RD. As such, the FLAIR-GG infrastructure has four primary components:

1. FAIR Metadata servers at every site, adhering to the FAIR Data Point^{6,7} (FDP) metadata specification. FAIR Data Points combine⁸ two existing Web standards - the Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT: <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>), and the Linked Data Platform (LDP: <https://www.w3.org/TR/ldp/>) to create a fully machine-traversable, hierarchical metadata record, capable of leading a computational agent to discover datasets, data access and/or analytical services.
2. A data transformation pipeline that depends on shared templates in the YARRRML⁹ language to convert CSV “dumps” of the native germplasm bank data into FAIR formats, following pre-formulated and shared semantic models based in the SemanticScience Integrated Ontology¹⁰ (SIO) and the FAO-IPGRI Multi-Passport Descriptor Ontology (<https://w3id.org/fao-ipgr>)
3. A dynamic index of all FDPs that have registered themselves to appear in the FLAIR-GG Network.
4. A portal that explores all registered partners and distributes queries or analytical requests to each site that has advertised (in their FDP metadata record) that they are capable and willing to accept such a request.

Components 1 and 2 are shown in Figure 1, while component 4 is diagrammed in Figure 2.

Fig. 1 The lower horizontal workflow shows the export of metadata describing the germplasm bank, and the nature of the data it holds, into a FAIR Data Point. This includes metadata describing any interfaces that might exist that allow exploration of the data itself (Meta A/B/C in the diagram). The upper workflow shows the data transformation pipeline that uses CSV as an intermediate representation between the native germplasm database, and the final FAIR data that appears in the Triplestore. Pre-configured and shared YARRRML templates are used to direct the transformation of the CSV into RDF, which is then published in the triplestore. Any interfaces (Service A/B/C) into the data are then pointed at this FAIR representation, rather than the database itself, enabling interoperability between non-coordinating germplasm banks.

The FLAIR-GG Network “Onboarding” Process

The process for onboarding a new resource into the Network is distributed and only loosely controlled (at this time) to reduce as much as possible barriers-to-entry for early adopters (complete instructions are available on the project Website: <https://wilkinsonlab.github.io/FLAIR-GG/>). The minimum requirements to join the network are:

- To have a FDP that contains at least the core metadata about your germplasm bank.
- Within that metadata record, “flag” the portions you wish to be indexed.
- Notify the central index of the URL of your FDPs Web address.

The content of the metadata is only minimally governed by the Platform, and attempts to align with the minimal requirements defined by the European DCAT Application Profile Version 3 (<https://semiceu.github.io/DCAT-AP/releases/3.0.0/>); however, providers are strongly encouraged to provide richer metadata records that will assist Platform users to discover them. In addition, there is a project specific metadata element that is used to designate which portions of the larger DCAT record the provider wishes to be searchable on the Platform, thus giving them the opportunity to opt-out of announcing any portion of their data holdings. Once the DCAT record is published, the provider sends the URL of that record to a central index, and they are then explored by the Platform, which gathers core information such as the URL, publisher, title, description, the nature of the resources exposed (Catalog, Dataset, Service, etc.) and keywords or ontology terms that have been provided for the purpose of discovery.

The data transformation and publication workflow shown in Figure 1 is optional, and entirely under the control of the Platform participant - all or selected parts of their data may be transformed in a manner compatible with the Platform’s shared ontological models, and after transformation the FAIR data may be kept entirely private, may be partially exposed in a Triplestore, or may be made available via one or more shared Platform services that query or analyse the data, and provide only the output results.

Examples of Anticipated Benefits

Examples of the benefit of joining the FLAIR-GG network will be the ability to (more) accurately assess the geographical areas that are under represented in national and international germplasm banks due to the biases mentioned previously. The improvement in interoperability among FLAIR-GG network members means that not only is it possible to check for areas that have not yet been sampled by other germplasm banks, but also to enhance the information about those places by using data from environmental, soil, geographical, meteorological databases and other relevant data sources. Another example will be to monitor the relative abundance of a species between regions - certain species are abundant in some regions but scarce in others. With this information, germplasm banks can better focus their collection strategies to prioritize species that are universally under-represented. The obstacles to germplasm data sharing and integration makes these kinds of comparisons complicated and frustrating using current approaches. The more participants who join the FLAIR-GG network, the more accurately these kinds of important integrative comparisons can be made, leading to better conservation strategies.

An Open Invitation

While this is only a superficial descriptor of the aims and functionality of the FLAIR-GG network and portal, more details are available on the project website linked above. The core FLAIR-GG infrastructure is largely complete, and we are now inviting third-party germplasm resources to join the network. The authors will be pleased to assist with your deployment, and are even willing to host your FDP on a short-term basis if you wish to explore participation with minimal commitment and minimal expense. We hope that FLAIR-GG provides a pathway towards more optimal usage of our valuable global germplasm resources.

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Ethics declarations

Competing interests

The corresponding author is co-founder of a consulting company that specializes in FAIR data infrastructures.

References

1. Wilkinson, M. D. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci. Data* **3**, 160018 (2016).
2. W3C. RDF - Semantic Web Standards. <http://www.w3.org/RDF/>.
3. Group, W. O. W. OWL 2 Web Ontology Language Document Overview (Second Edition). <http://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-overview/>.
4. FAO. *The Second Report on the State of the World's Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture*. Rome. <http://www.fao.org/docrep/013/i1500e/i1500e.pdf> (2010).
5. Shrestha, R. *et al.* Bridging the phenotypic and genetic data useful for integrated breeding through a data annotation using the Crop Ontology developed by the crop communities of practice. *Front. Physiol.* **3**, (2012).
6. Bonino Da Silva Santos, L. O. *et al.* FAIR Data Points Supporting Big Data Interoperability. in *Enterprise Interoperability in the Digitized and Networked Factory of the Future* (eds. Zelm, M., Doumeingts, G. & Mendonça, J. P.) 270–279 (iSTE Press, 2016).
7. da Silva Santos, L. O. B., Burger, K., Kaliyaperumal, R. & Wilkinson, M. D. FAIR Data Point: A FAIR-Oriented Approach for Metadata Publication. *Data Intell.* **5**, 163–183 (2023).
8. Wilkinson, M. D. *et al.* Interoperability and FAIRness through a novel combination of Web technologies. *PeerJ Comput. Sci.* **3**, e110 (2017).
9. Heyvaert, P., De Meester, B., Dimou, A. & Verborgh, R. Declarative Rules for Linked Data Generation at Your Fingertips! in *The Semantic Web: ESWC 2018 Satellite Events* (eds. Gangemi, A. *et al.*) vol. 11155 213–217 (Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2018).
10. Dumontier, M. *et al.* The SemanticScience Integrated Ontology (SIO) for biomedical research and knowledge discovery. *J. Biomed. Semant.* **5**, 14 (2014).